

Mobile Phone-Linked Infection Risks: A Survey of Awareness, Hygiene Practices and Associated Factors Among Mobile Phone Users in Ijebu-Ode, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Mobile phones have become an integral part of our daily lives, and their cleanliness and potential health hazards are often overlooked, constituting significant health risks, primarily due to the potential for bacterial contamination. However, despite their widespread use, evidence points to low level of awareness and inconsistent hygiene practices among mobile phone users. As a result, this population-based study examined the awareness of infection transmission risks, hygiene practices, and related factors among mobile phone users in Ijebu-Ode, Nigeria.

Methods: A semi-structured self-administered questionnaire was employed to gather data from 580 residents of Ijebu-Ode physically and virtually, utilising a cross-sectional descriptive survey design, and analysed using SPSS 23 with Pearson Correlation Coefficient to determine the relationship between variables at $P < 0.05$ level of significance.

Results: Findings indicate overall low level of knowledge of the risks of mobile phone infection transmission among majority of the participants (weighted mean = 3.45 < 3.50 threshold) and majority (62.5%) exhibited poor mobile phone hygiene practices. Among other factors, the fear of damage (32.0%) was the major reason given by participants for not cleaning their mobile phones. A statistically significant correlation was observed between exposure to mobile phone-cleaning education and improved hygiene practices ($P < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Our findings demonstrate a critical gap in knowledge and the need for targeted educational interventions to improve hygiene practices to reduce the risk of infection transmission through mobile phones in public.

Keywords: Infection Risk, Infection Transmission, Mobile Phone Hygiene, Nigeria

Introduction

Mobile phones (MPs) have become widely used worldwide and have profoundly influenced communication, information access, and lifestyle in various domains.¹ Consequently, they have become an indispensable accessory for both professional and social life.² While MPs are acknowledged and used extensively in all facets of human activities, there have been concerns about their potential to transmit infections within the public health space.³⁻⁶ For example, a study has shown that the transmission of infections through MPs presents a significant global public health issue, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, including Nigeria, where there has been a concerning rise in the number of MP users across various age groups and socioeconomic backgrounds.⁷ Studies have shown that the rate of bacterial contamination on hands increased to 93.7% after using MPs with evidence public health impact.⁸⁻¹²

As such, while MPs are indispensable in contemporary professional and social life, they also pose significant health risks due to their role in spreading bacterial infections.² For instance, a study on the potential role of MPs in spreading bacterial infections indicated that MP, often in constant contact with users' hands and faces, serve as reservoirs for various pathogenic bacteria.⁷ These bacteria can easily be transferred from contaminated surfaces to mobile devices and users, increasing the risk of infection. Similarly, recent studies on the implications of MP usage on health demonstrated that frequent handling of MPs increases the likelihood of microbial transfer.^{13, 14} Furthermore, the bacterial communities found on MPs closely resemble those on the owners' hands, thus suggesting that MPs do not only act as vectors for potentially harmful pathogens but also mirror the personal microbiome of their users, effectively serving as extensions of the human body.¹⁴ Hence, these findings collectively underscore the health risks associated with MP usage, highlighting the role of MPs in microbial exchange and the potential for infection transmission.

However, despite many studies on the public health implications of MP usage, there is a lack of population-based studies, as previous

investigations have mainly focused on isolating harmful microorganisms from MPs, particularly among specific groups such as students^{3, 5, 15} and health professionals.^{4, 16, 17} While these studies have been valuable in revealing harmful microorganisms on MPs, their emphasis on specific populations overlooks the diverse patterns of MP usage and hygiene practices among the general population and limits the generalizability of their findings. The use of MPs spans all demographics, and their potential role in transmitting infections is a public health concern beyond specific social or occupational environments. This primarily overlooked area in previous studies highlights the need for population-based studies to understand better the widespread and significant risk of MP contamination among the general population in Ijebu-Ode, Nigeria.

As such, our study not only addressed the current knowledge gap but also provided a more representative dataset for holistic understanding of the public health risks associated with MP usage, giving insights for future research, guidelines and policies development in related areas.

Methodology

Study area

The City of Ijebu-Ode is about sixty kilometres north-west of Lagos with a geographical area of 192 km² and a population of 381,000 with a 3.53% growth rate from 2022.¹⁸ Being a populous ancient city in Ogun State, Nigeria, Ijebu-Ode is well known for several educational, cultural, and economic activities, attracting a massive population and hosting different social groups across the globe annually, especially during popular cultural festivals. Thus, public places in the study area such as markets, educational institutions, health institutions, hotels, industries, recreational, cultural, and religious centres, clubs, motor parks, and film houses, may subject the population to a high risk of MP infection transmission.

Study design, sample size and sampling

The research adopted a cross-sectional descriptive survey design. The minimum sample size (n) was

determined to be 400, using Taro Yamane formula; $n = N/(1+N(e)^2)$ ^{18, 21} where n = minimum sample size, $N = 381,000$ (population to be studied¹⁸), and $e = 0.05$ (margin of error allowed). Subsequently, a purposive sampling technique was adopted in selecting the respondents.

Data collection and analysis

Data was collected from 580 respondents using a semi-structured self-administered questionnaire adapted from previous studies,^{19,20} via Google Forms distributed online and administered physically with the help of four trained research assistants. Only consenting respondents voluntarily participated online. The Google Forms questionnaires were distributed through various social media group platforms for interested participants to fill out. Also, various places in the community were visited including educational institutions, health institutions, marketplaces, residential premises, streets, worship centres, business centres, and farms to administer hard copies of the questionnaires to consenting individuals after discussing the study's purpose with each of them. Data collected was analysed using the SPSS 23 version and presented appropriately in simple frequency tables, bars and pie charts for straightforward interpretation. Hypotheses were tested using the Pearson Correlation Coefficient to determine the relationship between selected variables with a significance level of $P < 0.05$.

Knowledge and practice classification

We adapted knowledge and practice classification as outlined in a previous study.²⁰ For level of knowledge/awareness determination, each item in the questionnaire with a five point Likert scale was assessed using descriptive statistics such as means (M) and standard deviations (SD). Mean value was used to assess the central tendency of responses for interpretation and 3.50 threshold was set. $M \geq 3.50$ indicates good knowledge (more responses skewed toward "Aware" and "Totally Aware") while $M < 3.50$ indicates poor knowledge (more responses around "Undecided", "Unaware", or "Totally Unaware"). Also, for

determination of hygiene practice level, MP hygiene practices were categorized as good and poor respectively. Practice scores range from 0 to 8, and each correct answer was given a score of 1 and 0 for wrong response. As such, respondents with good practice obtained scores between 4 and 8 ($\geq 50\%$), while any score between 0 and 3 ($< 50\%$) was adjudged poor.

Results

This survey assessed the awareness of mobile phone infection transmission risks, hygiene practice levels, and associated factors among 580 mobile phone users in Ijebu-Ode, Nigeria. The *demographic characteristics of respondents in Table 1* shows that males constituted 103 (17.8%) and females are 477 (82.2%) respondents. Majority (59.0%) of the respondents were between the age ranges of 21-30 years and the least age range (0.7%) fell below 11 years. Majority (81.2%) of them had tertiary education and a minority (18.8%) were of lower educational levels. Also, most (75.0%) of them were students while very few (1.4%) were civil servants.

In Table 2, respondents' awareness level of mobile phone infection risks with weighted Average Mean Value (AMV) of 3.45. Respondents showed low levels of awareness with mean values less than AMV ($< 3.42, < 3.38, < 3.37, < 3.23$) with respect to sharing MPs with others, retention and growth of pathogens on MPs, increased contamination of MPs without pouches and MPs being ten times dirtier than a toilet seat respectively. However, on the other hand, some showed a considerably high levels of awareness with respective mean values greater than the AMV ($> 3.66, > 3.56, > 3.48$) with regards to MP contamination through dirty hands, when used in the kitchen, toilet or workplace and when held with lips or with neck and shoulder while doing other things. The overall mean was 3.45, indicating poor level of awareness/knowledge among respondents ($3.45 < 3.50$ threshold).

Furthermore, the level of mobile phone hygiene practice among respondents shown in Table 3 indicates that 61(10.5%) never cleaned their MPs, 118(20.3%) did occasionally, and 401(69.1%) did always. However, among those who did clean their

MPs, 61(10.5%) of them used cloth, 423(72.9%) used tissue paper, and 96(16.6%) used the recommended cleaning agent (70% alcohol based fluid). In the same vein, while 267(46.0%) of the respondents never washed their hands before and after handling their MPs, 247(42.6%) of them did sometimes and 66(11.4%) of them did always. Also, while 250 (43.1%) of the respondents never washed their hands, 235(40.5%) did washed their hands with water only, 95(16.4%) did with water and soap or used sanitizer. The percentage summary indicates that only 37.5% of the respondents had good MP hygiene practices, while majority (62.5%) had poor practices.

Also, 262(32.0%) of the respondents did not clean their MPs due to fear of phone damage, 234(29.0%) due to *unbelief that MPs carry disease agents*, 128(16.0%) lacked knowledge of MP cleaning, 120(15.0%) lacked the time and 8.0% felt it was unnecessary (Figure 1). Figure 2 shows respondents' exposure to MP hygiene education and only 174 (38.0%) had learnt how to clean their MPs before, 280 (62.0%) had not. Figure 3 indicates that, 264 (44.0%) never learnt MP cleaning by any means, 105 (18.0%) of them learnt through social media or online, 38.0% learnt through other means. Furthermore, Table 4 indicates that respondents' awareness level and hygiene practice had a weak positive correlation co-efficient value ($r = 0.059$) with no statistically significant association ($p = 0.154$) and their formal education status versus hygiene practice had a weak negative correlation value ($r = -0.020$) with no statistically significant association ($p = 0.314$). However, there was a statistically significant association between mobile-phone cleaning education and hygiene practice level ($r = 0.123$, $p = 0.003$).

Table 1: Socio-demographical characteristics of respondents

Variable	Frequency (n= 580)	Percentage
Sex:		
Male	103	17.8
Female	477	82.2
Age:		
= 11years	4	0.7
11-20 years	131	22.6
21-30 years	342	59.0
31-40 years	80	13.8
Above 40 years	23	4.0
Marital status		
Not married	466	80.5
Married	112	19.3
Widow/ Widower	1	0.2
Educational level		
No formal Education	20	3.4
Primary	4	0.7
Secondary	85	14.7
Tertiary	471	81.2
Employment		
Civil Servant	8	1.4
Private employee	100	17.2
Self-Employed	37	6.4
Students (in school)	394	67.9

Table 2: Respondents' level of awareness/knowledge of mobile phone infection risks

Awareness Variables (n = 580)	TU f (%)	U f (%)	UD f (%)	A f (%)	TA f (%)	M (S.D)	Decision
Mobile phones can retain and grow harmful microorganisms such as bacteria, viruses and fungi.	64(11.0)	156(26.9)	46(7.9)	125(21.6)	189(32.6)	3.38(1.4)	Low
Infections can be contracted or transferred through the use or sharing of mobile phones.	48(8.3)	149(25.7)	67(11.6)	144(24.8)	172(29.7)	3.42(1.4)	Low
Mobile phones grow and multiply microorganisms faster when their temperature increases.	28(4.8)	174(30.0)	78(13.4)	126(21.7)	174(30.0)	3.42(1.3)	Low
Dirty or contaminated hands can transmit disease agents to mobile phones and vice versa.	36(6.2)	92(15.9)	81(14.0)	194(33.4)	177(30.5)	3.66(1.2)	High
Mobile phones can be contaminated when used in the kitchen, toilet or workplace.	32(5.5)	119(20.5)	71(12.2)	157(27.1)	201(34.7)	3.65(1.3)	High
Mobile phones are ten times dirtier than toilet seats.	56(9.7)	179(30.9)	90(15.5)	86(14.8)	169(29.1)	3.23(1.4)	Low
A phone without a pouch promotes contamination.	32(5.5)	167(28.8)	103(17.8)	113(19.5)	165(28.4)	3.37(1.3)	Low
Holding the phone on the lips, neck, and shoulder while doing other things can transmit infections.	48(8.3)	129(22.2)	74(12.8)	155(26.7)	174(30.0)	3.48(1.3)	Low
SUMMARY:							
Overall Mean = 3.45							
Threshold = 3.50							
Overall Level of Knowledge: Low (3.45 < 3.50 Threshold)							

TU=Totally Unaware; U=Unaware; UD = Undecided; A=Aware; TA=Totally Aware; Unawareness Level (UL) = TU+U; Awareness Level (AL) = TA+A; f=frequency; Decision rule: Mean Value ? 3.50 has low awareness and mean value = 3.50 has high awareness

Table 3: Respondents' Mobile Phone Hygiene Practices

Practices Variable (f = 580)	Never (%)	Sometimes (%)	Always (%)	Decision
Take the mobile phone to the toilet or kitchen.	77(13.3)**	422(72.8)*	81(14.0)*	Poor
Share mobile phone (s) with another person.	65(11.2)**	406(70.0)*	109(18.8)*	Poor
Hold the phone with lips or neck and shoulder.	135(23.3)**	409(70.5)*	36(6.2)*	Poor
Use a pouch with the phone	112(19.3)*	182(31.4)**	286(49.3)**	Good
Frequency of mobile phone cleaning	61(10.5)*	118(20.3)**	401(69.1)**	Good
Mobile phone cleaning material used	(C) 61(10.5)*	(TP) 423(72.9)*	(RCA)96(16.6)**	Poor
Hand washing before and after handling mobile phone	267(46.0)*	247(42.6)**	66(11.4)**	Good
Hand wash materials	(N) 250(43.1)*	(WO) 235(40.5)*	(WSS)95(16.4)**	Poor

Summary of General MP Hygiene Practices:

Good (= 50%)
37.5%
 Low (< 50%)
62.5%

****Positive Practice *Negative Practice; C = Cloth; TP = Tissue paper; RCA = Recommended Cleaning Agent; N = Nothing; WO = Water only; WSS = Water with Soap/Sanitizer**

Figure 1: Respondents' reasons for not cleaning their phones

Figure 2: Respondents' exposure to mobile phone hygiene education

Figure 3: Means of mobile phone cleaning education

Table 4: Correlations between MP Hygiene Practice and Selected variables

Hypothetic Variables	r	P
Awareness level Versus Hygiene Practice Level	0.059	0.154
Education Status Versus Hygiene Practice Level	-0.020	0.314
Mobile-Phone Cleaning Education Versus Hygiene Practice Level	0.123*	0.003

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Discussion

The study explored awareness of mobile phone infection transmission risks, hygiene practices, and associated factors among mobile phone users in Ijebu-Ode, Nigeria. Findings indicate poor knowledge/awareness of MP infection risks among majority of residents of Ijebu-Ode, suggesting that the residents are unaware of the risk of MP infection transmission, leading to increase risk of exposure to infections. Detail observation shows that some residents were less aware regarding the retention and growth of harmful microorganisms such as bacteria, viruses and fungi on MPs, microbial transmission through the use or sharing of MPs with others, and awareness that MPs are ten times dirtier than a toilet seat. This current finding is consistent with previous studies which documented low MP infection awareness among the study population.²⁰

²¹ However, in contrast to our finding, other previous findings have shown variant results that most participants were aware of MPs acting as fomites.^{10,17,23} Also, another study reported that a large number of the study population were aware that *microbial agents* are on MPs.¹⁹ The Variation in levels of awareness or knowledge of MPs contamination risks among participants in our study compared with previous studies may be attributed to differences in socio-demographic and training background of participants. Participants in the previous studies are mostly health professionals or medical students who may have had prior knowledge of poor hygiene risks due to their health training exposure, while our study constituted heterogeneous population, being population-based. Our study predicts that majority of the population who were less aware of this risk may not engage in MP hygiene practices and subsequently, may be at risks of related infections. This current finding corresponds with a previous study which reported that respondents with high level of knowledge were more likely to clean their phones compared to those with low level of knowledge.²⁰

Regarding MP hygiene practice, results indicate that few of the respondents **had** good MP hygiene practice **as against the majority who poorly practised MP hygiene. Findings revealed unhealthy attitude towards MP hygiene**

practices among a significant majority of the residents who sometimes took their MPs to the toilet or kitchen, shared their MPs with other people, held their phone with neck and shoulder when making calls and who never washed their hands before and after handling their MP. Thus, there is evidence of poor MP hygiene practices among residents of in Ijebu-Ode. These findings agree with previous studies which documented that more than half of the residents in study population used MPs in unhygienic ways such as using them in the washrooms, indicating low MP hygiene.^{9, 20} Similarly, a cross-sectional study in Edinburgh revealed that more than average respondents had never cleaned their phones.²³ However, contrary to our findings, a study conducted among medical students reported that most of the study participants cleaned their phones.²⁰ The medical training experience among participants in the previous study compared with those ones in our population-based study may likely explain the variation in MP hygiene practices. In this survey, some of the participants indicated that they cleaned their MPs regularly, though not with the recommended cleaning agent, but with ordinary tissue papers and clothes, signifying unhealthy MP hygiene practice. Thus, this indicates the exposure of MP users to potential risk of MP-linked infection transmissions in the population. Our findings have consistently agreed with previous studies which demonstrated poor MP cleaning practices among study participants.^{10, 20}

Regarding factors influencing MP hygiene practice, findings show that the main reason respondents did not clean their phones is fear of phone damage. Other reasons include unbelief on MPs carrying disease agents, lack of MP cleaning knowledge or skills and time factor. Thus, this may further discourage MP hygiene practices and increase the risks of MP-related infection transmission in the population. Our current finding is consistent with an existing study which reported that unhealthy practices could be linked with misconceptions about cell phone damage caused by antibacterial wipes among users.²⁴ Similarly, another finding shows that MPs cleaning and disinfection of MPs is a rare practice among most users.¹¹ Furthermore, our finding

shows that a higher percentage of respondents never cleaned their MPs because they were not exposed to MP hygiene education, suggesting lack of MP cleaning skills among the respondents. However, a very few of them indicated they learned MP cleaning through social media, seminar or workshop, phone manuals and friends or relatives. This points to the indispensable roles of multi-media platforms in conveying MP cleaning education interventions. This finding is in line with existing study which reported the effectiveness of mass media such as newspapers, TV, and radio in improving hygiene practices in infectious disease prevention.²⁵ Thus, our findings support the importance of creating public awareness via media education, organised workshops and public seminars on MP hygiene practices to reduce MP associated infection risks.

Furthermore, findings indicate that there was no statistically significant relationship between knowledge of MP infection transmission risk and the practice of MP hygiene. This finding implies that the level of awareness/knowledge of mobile phone infection transmission risks among residents of Ijebu-Ode does not influence their MP hygiene practices. Similarly, our findings report no statistically significant correlation between respondents' formal education status and mobile phone hygiene practice level, implying that the formal education status of participants does not influence their practice of MP hygiene. This finding agrees with that of a study in Malaysia, which documented a lack of significant relationship between knowledge level, among other factors, and MP cleaning practices, suggesting that knowledge of MP-linked infection risk does not always translate into hygiene practices.^{19,20} However, further observation shows a statistically significant relationship between respondents' exposure to MP-cleaning education and hygiene practice level, suggesting the importance of MP cleaning education in promoting MP hygiene practice and safeguarding public health.

Study implications and limitations

This study makes significant contributions to the field of public health, particularly shedding light on the behavioural patterns related to MP hygiene

by identifying the key factors influencing these practices, thus promoting public health in the context of infection prevention. Nevertheless, being a cross-sectional study, the study could not measure causal relationship between MP education and hygiene practices. As such, we suggest a longitudinal study to provide more insight over an extended period in future researches or a focus on developing interventional strategies.

Conclusion

This study assessed the knowledge of mobile phone infection transmission risks, hygiene practice levels, and associated factors among mobile phone users in Ijebu-Ode. Findings indicate that, majority of the participants were not aware of infection transmission risks associated with mobile phone usage and did not practice good MP hygiene, thus likely to increase the risk of infection exposure and transmission among users. Poor MP hygiene practice among users was due to many factors, including fear of MP damage. There was a statistically significant relationship between MP hygiene practice level and MP hygiene education exposure among respondents but not with knowledge of mobile phone infection transmission risks and formal educational status. Hence, community-based health education, public policy and enactment of law on MP hygiene practice are necessary in promoting MP hygiene practice among users.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare the absence of competing interests.

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